

Tsallis Constraints $\sum(i) e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{ave}$ and $\sum(i) p(e_i) = 1$ Mapping to One Constraint $\sum(i) p(e_i) = 1$?

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It is possible to solve for the Tsallis distribution by maximizing Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)^q)$ (with $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$) subject to the two constraints $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. One may argue that $p(e_i)^q$ has physical meaning and the result is a power law $(e_i/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$ (and $(1+(1-q)(-e_i/T))^{1/(1-q)}$ in general. Alternatively, one may seek a power law distribution which behaves as $(e_i/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ (we write the power as $1/(1-q)$) and then ask: What $g(p)$ in the constraint $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) e_i$ together with $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ allows for $-\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i))$ to be maximized. In this way one may find $g = p^q$.

We suggest here that there exists a second way to consider the maximization of entropy problem. We argue that instead of seeking two independent constraints $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) e_i = E_{ave}$ (where $g(p) = p^q$) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$, one may maximize entropy subject to a single constraint, i.e. $\sum_i g(p) e_i$ becomes proportional to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. In other words, one solves a differently constrained system with the a priori knowledge that $p(e_i)$ behaves as $(e_i/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$.

Solving for the Tsallis Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is solved by maximizing Shannon's entropy:

$$-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ subject to } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((1))$$

One might try to generalize this approach and consider maximizing:

$$-\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i)) \text{ subject to } \sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{Number} \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

Here $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. ((3)) One may note that $p(e_i)^q$ has a physical interpretation (i.e. a probability is multiplied q times).

$$\text{If one sets: } dF/dp \ p^q = 1 \text{ then } F(p) = (1 + (1-q) p^q) / (1-q) \quad ((4))$$

so that ((4)) becomes $\ln(p)$ when $q=1$. Given that F is the inverse of p , one has:

$$p(e_i) = (1 + (1-q)(-e_i/T))^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{This becomes } (e_i/T)^{1/(1-q)} \text{ for } e_i/T \gg 1 \quad ((6))$$

Experimentally, one sees such power law drop-off distributions in nature and ((6)) seems reasonable.

We now try to solve this problem in a slightly different manner by using $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}$ as a constraint without explicitly setting $g(p) = p(e_i)^{-q}$. We, however, require that $p(e_i)$ behave as $(e_i/T)^{-q}$ for $(e_i/T) \gg 1$. If one solves this problem in a region where $(e_i/T) \gg 1$, then:

$$g(p) \frac{dF}{dp} = 1 \quad ((7))$$

In this region $p = (e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)}$ (we choose $1/(1-q)$ to describe the power law drop-off). Given that F is the inverse of p , F must behave as:

$$F(p) = -(e_i/T) = -p^{-1/(1-q)} \quad \text{so } dF/dp \text{ goes as } -p^{-q} \text{ and } g(p) = p^{-q} \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the previous result is obtained without assuming a priori a $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^{-q} = \text{number}$ constraint.

Both of the above approaches, however, use two constraints just like the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

Using One Constraint

We suggest considering the problem in the following manner. We seek a distribution which becomes:

$$(e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)} \text{ for } e_i/T \gg 1 \quad ((9))$$

Instead of using two constraints that are independent, we use a single one:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((10)) \text{ which should always hold.}$$

We ask: What $g(p)$ makes $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) e_i \rightarrow \sum_i p(e_i)$?

We still retain entropy as: $-\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i))$ such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

In the region, $e_i/T \gg 1$, one has:

$$g((e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)}) \text{ and } e_i = p^{-1/(1-q)} \quad ((11))$$

$$g(p) p^{-1/(1-q)} = p \quad \text{or} \quad g(p) = p^{1-q} \quad ((12))$$

In this manner one then find $g(p)$ and may maximize

$$-\sum_i p(e_i)^{-q} F(p(e_i)) \text{ subject to } \sum_i e_i p(e_i)^{-q} \text{ and } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((13))$$

keeping in mind that both constraints must ultimately be proportional to each other.

This yields $p(e_i) = (1 + (1-q)(-e_i/T))^{-1/(1-q)}$ ((14))

One might argue that one already assumed a distribution which behaves as $(e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)}$ ((15)) for $e_i/T \gg 1$ and so one essentially knows the distribution to begin with. One may create the form ((15)) such that $e_i/T \rightarrow 0$ or $q \rightarrow 1$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The point is that we wish to show that this power law Tsallis distribution may be linked with maximization of entropy subject to constraints. It seems to be an equilibrium type of distribution, but a relaxed one with a constraint essentially on $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. The Tsallis system is differently constrained than the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

One may then ask: What is the meaning of T given that ((14)) is unnormalized. One would expect that T follows from

$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = \text{Number}$ ((15))

and that different values of Number yield different T values. This seems to be the case, but the constraint ((15)) is also proportional to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and so one does not have two completely independent constraints even if Number may be varied, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may maximize entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i)^q F(p)$ where $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ subject to the two constraints $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = \text{Number}$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and obtain the Tsallis distribution such that $q=1$ yields $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Alternatively, we show here that one may assume a power law distribution $(e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)}$ for $(e_i/T) \gg 1$ and assume the single constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = \text{number}$. In other words, one may argue that $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i))$ is proportional to $\sum_i p(e_i)$ and then find that $g = p(e_i)^q$ if p behaves as $(e_i/T)^{-1/(1-q)}$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$.